

t u s t u s j r w f g e

at;at;cilf*

pmwrft uof

avmuü vlvbni tvs' getrsdruul vrsdtvlu? bmontvluif jykly/vsuif
&uygon/ a&bt;ES tze/yryg aEGrSod 'geES tolvryg aocgrSod[haom pum; twlf
&cV&om vlvOwlf rrvlvN ypinfOpms;rS 'getEpiul xkvi, lwwluap&el
rvlvay;v&aom tvs\weztuul o&drfajrmuujyð wwpf;Eil br&aom vszG f
rsm;uul p&luay;urfvs' getluap&ef &n&G li 'ge\t'yth, ES h oabmvuPmsm?
tvS' geES tywouli rsvom; zG &msm;? tvS' getrsdruul jci fjzi h &&Eil rnh tust
w&m; rsm; uul polawoepmwrfwof avlvmwif yxm; ygon/
aontsupum; vlrsm/ / 'ge? apwem? OwR tavmb? p&luajci? ur& uwÓPi

edgef

b&m; &S fyð lawmrrhD a&sumvrsm; uyif 'gew&m; onf toftrsdruul jzi h &eygon/
jA [PwN a [majymrt& vlvbni aumifre&mb0a&mu&a&; twlf owðgwltm;
owjzwif , ZlybZmrsm; uul 'ge [bwrsvxi jri ybZm&luon/ b&m; &S fyð lawmrl
vmaomtcg , ZlybZmjci f \ tjyptuul a [mji abm*orlv& jynp&; twlf tvsjk
vlyenf 'geuxmsm; uul a [majymawmr&bn/ 'geapwemonf o' gw&m; xubeb?
arw&rtm; luðrm; oN oEheluomjzpb&v&bn/ p&luay;urfvs' getjcionf arw&
w&m; uul um, u&ajrmuf usi b&aejci fjzpon/ Oelwtr(rp&d) vlt; si fywrufl (avmb)
w&m; wluul w&f v&Eil rsm tvs' geul jylEil luon/ owðgwN oEhelwof v&pb
x&jymv&aom avmbw&m; uul w&f v&Eil rsm tvs' geul jylEil luon/ xlvmb
w&m; uul w&f v&Eil , lowEil &ef 'gerjzi h avlusi h &ayrn/ ypinf wptuul vsygu
, ifypinf tay: p&vefaom avmbwptuul y, lowEil jyjzpon/ xlv&umi h 'gerluul
lu&rfzerm; p&h jykly/bbnf arw&w&m; yb; rsm; rl rp&d y, h? avmby, riul lu&rfz
rsm; p&h jykly/b&ejci fjzpon/ ay;urfvs' getrl&umi h pnf p&drp& luG Dcstfomol
jzpEil jyd tv&v&wlf tustcyonf fjyðp&Eil l&umi f uul avmuev&dgxmv&f]] 'geth oA&v-
om" u]] [li azmf yxm; ygon/ 'geonf vrs&lbomra&G rrvlv wwpf;Eil bavmu fzi h
'geublvtrsdruul jykly/v&uygon/ vlrsm; uul p&vlusef rmcstfomapv&om
apwemjzi haq; &h&q; cefrsm; aqmu/vly/vs' getjci f? pmoih&usmif rsm; aqmu/vly/vs' get
jci f? aogvs' getjci f? cEmuul ft p&v tyll rsm; vs' getjci f? vlyftm; tvs ay; v&luajci f?
ab; 'lu&luaw&aomorsm;? Eil li rsm; oN vlt y&m&m axmu/vly; jci f ponjzi h 'getrsd
ruul jykly/luayon/

* uxlu? ta&lv&wlf fynm&me? ybt; wuio&lv
1/ avmuev&dv 230/

tcsthaom olwlonf tvsday;&mwlf &wemohyg;ull vsrbom tvs[li xifrif
 MUYgonf]]tvscwvplustav;? ac&utpvsaumifon}} [kaom tqtt & w&paiefull
 au&argcifoniyif tvsrnygonf/ tvsulykly&mu t, w? tvw? tjrwwra&&
 ay;v&Elygonf/ p&v&apwemaumiijzih ay;v&sygu jzpbav&mb0wlf tus&trsm;yull
 ppmwrfwlf azmfyxm;ygonf/ vlttylon&e&mu vltty&m&mr&forull ay;v&sjcifonf
 tvs'geyijzplygonf/ r&wly;v&saom tvs\ tus&ausZt;Mudri rnf&B&bnful
 o&ap&ef ppmwrfwlf tvs'ge\ oabmvuPmrsm;? tvs'getrs&trsd? tvs'ge&S h
 ywouf r&v&om;z& &mrsm;? tv&syjciijzih &&f&nh tus&ausZt;rsn;ull avhvmwify
 xm;ygonf/

tcef(1)

tvS'ge\ t''yij, Esh oabmvuPmrsn

vllwllfvllwllfonl tvsa&puvlu&ruhu wwlftm;oa&0 p&elluay;urf vs'gef,luayg onl/ b0ob&mrS rv&v&ajrmufrcsil ypl&y&? wrv&e&umifust& crt,om&&ap&ef 'ge rlu&y&luaygonl/ 'ge? olv? bm0emv&bnf Ar'bmomOifwll&f usi&aqmi&lu&y&rt&aom vlyif&ef(p&P)jzplonl/ Ar'0g' \ yef,wll&fn b0'lu&S v&v&ajrmu&a&;yijzplonl/ xll yef,wll&fn&mu&&ef usi&lu&tr(p&P)rsm; jy&vly&onl/ usi&lu&tr(p&P)atmi&fri&om t&cgop&nav;yg;u&ll xll&x&0&fo&jri&om r*O&P&u&ll&&bnl/ xllt&cg b0'lu&Sv&v&ajrmuf Ell&ayonl/ o&A&h&kw&b&&m;&S&f u&ll& h&aw&mr&w&lu&lonlyif b&&m; jzpl&e&av; oac&ES h ur&fn wpl&e&f,wll& h&atmi&f yg&r&tr&sm; jzn&usi&lc&h&ayonl/ yg&r&tr&sm; jzn&usi&lc&mw&v&fn&f y&pn&f vs'gef,p&ellu&rl 'geyg&r&D(Am[&u b@m y&f&pn&a*g 'geyg&r&Demr)? v&u&aj&cpaom t*f&u&ll vs'gef,p&ellu&rl 'geOyyg&r&D(t*f&y&f&pn&a*g 'geOyyg&r&Demr)? tou&u&ll vs'gef, p&ellu&rl 'gey&r&w&yg&r&D(ZD&v&y&f&pn&a*g 'gey&r&w&yg&r&Demr)w&lu&ll O&pp&h&jzn&usi&lc&h&ayonl² xll&lu&mi&h&t&vs'geonl yg&r&lu&b&ll&vlyif&ef t&p&pk&v&ll& rlv&t&aj&c&h&kw&lr&pl&jzpl&ygonl/

1;1/ tvS'ge\ t''yij, f

'ge[h&om yg&v&0g[m&onl o'gen&t& 'g+, k (e)jzpl& ay;jcif? ay;urtj&icif? tv&S ay;jcif³[k t''yij, &onl/ jref&mt&b&meft&w&S (2)ü ay;urt&p&ellu&jcif⁴ [k az&mf&y&x&m;yg onl/ xll ge[h&om yg&v&0g[m&u&lljref&ma0g[m&j&zi&hay;urtj&icif? vs'gef,j&icif? p&ellu&jcif? ya&Z&mf&icif[k teuft''yij, &0&lc&qu&onl/ tr&e&pi&pp&ft&m;j&zi&h 'ge[bn&f y&pn&f,0&wk w&pk&cl&u&ll p&ellu&ay;urf,vs'gef,j&icif,omru ow&D&gw&ll&t&m; ab;r&h&y;j&icif? ow&D&gw&ll&N tou&ft&tt&f&pn&f,pr&fu&ll ow&j&zw&v&k u&z&su&q&bj&icif,w&ll&S a&&ni&lu&O&j&icif? ow&D&gw&ll&t&m; ab;&eft&e&&m, ft&r&dr&st&w&ll&S umu&G& h&pmi&h&&ni&u&j&icif,on&v&n&f 'geyijzplonl/ xll&yif olw&py&g;t&m; ay;csi&? pm;ap&csi&? aom&u&h&ap&csi&? Ow&h&ap&csi&? use&r&map&csi&? crt,om ap&csi&? tou&&S&h&ap&csi& h&om apwem (p&v&v&x&m;)rsm;on&v&n&f 'gejy&f&ef t&aj&c&h&v&&m;rsm; jzplonl/ xll&lu&mi&h ay;urtj&icif? p&ellu&j&icif? aO&icif? r&0&v&j&icif? jzn&p&u&j&icif? c&sj&r&S& h&x&mu&y&j&icif? u&h&j&icif? vs'gef,q&u&f&y&j&icif pon&ht&r&tr&sm;u&ll jy&vly&v&om&apwem&v&n&f,aumi&f? ay;urf,p&ellu&ty&h&om y&pn&f,0&wk&rsm;u&ll v&n&f,aumi&f 'ge[kac:ygonl/

- (1) ay;v&Sv&h&om apwem&p&w&ol&u&ll 'ge[kac:onl/ apwem&f&S ay;v&S jzpl&N/ apwem&u&ll tv&S&rjzpl&y/ xll&lu&mi&h tv&S&jzpl&ajrmu&h&lu&mi&f apwem&u&ll 'ge[kac:onl/
- (2) apwem&ES h& h&om tav&mb&p&w&ol&u&ll&v&n&f 'ge[kac:onl/ y&pn&f&u& w&G& f&v&maom av&mb&&eol&u 'gerjzpl& w&G& f&v&mr&u&ifaom tav&mb&&bl&u om 'gejzpl&N/ xll&lu&mi&h apwem&ES h& h&om tav&mb&u&ll&v&n&f 'ge[kac: onl/

2/ ty? |? 1? 32/
3/ yg-jref-"mef 465/
4/ jref-"mef 171/

(t x m O & 'ge)? r r d t o u f x i & f r ; & p O v s j i c i f (o Z D 'ge)? a o o n b e m u f & n r f e f i v s j i c i f
 (t p o 'ge)? t m u o f t u e f t n h t z s i f u l v s j i c i f (O p d 'ge)? t r e f t j r w f y p o n f a u m i f u l
 v s j i c i f (t e p d 'ge)? w & m ; o j z i & a o m y p o n f u l v s j i c i f ("r p 'ge)? r w & m ; o j z i & a o m
 y p o n f u l v s j i c i f (t 'r p 'ge)? a e p O r j y w f q f f a v m i f v s j i c i f (e A ' 'ge)? a e p O r [k w l o l
 w w E l l b o n h t c g v s j i c i f (t e A ' 'ge)? o m ; i g ; w u l l o w f i v s j i c i f o n f t j y p f & f (o m O Z A
 'ge)? o m ; i g ; t a o u l l O , f i a y ; v s j i c i f o n f t j y p f & f (t e O Z A g e) ? u l l k w l l u l l l u s
 v u j z i h a y ; v s j i c i f (o [w u 'ge)? o l w p y g ; u h p c h f i v s j i c i f (t m P w u 'ge)? v s z G f
 O w k u h u m i f p h i y k i v s j i c i f (o u p d g e) ? v s z G O w k u h z p o v h a y ; v s j i c i f (t o u p d g e) ?
 x i h a y ; v l l a y ; v s j i c i f ([l e 'ge)? v e w t c r f o m u l l a w m i h v i a y ; v s j i c i f (r Z i r 'ge)? p s n e f
 r * z l v i u l l & n & G f i a y ; v s j i c i f (y P l w 'ge)? r r p m ; o h o n x u f , k w i n b o n i u l l a y ; v s j i c i f
 ('g o 'ge)? r r p m ; o h o u b h a y ; v s j i c i f (o [m , 'ge)? r r p m ; o h o n x u f j r i j r w o n i u l l
 a y ; v s j i c i f (o m r d g e) p o n z i h t r s t r s t & l u o n f /

t v s 'g e j y k o n b q & m u r r p o w u w p t k w n f a q m i f i j y o n f [k w / t z a v a g e ?
 O w k g e [k a c : a o m E p j z m t r l j y n p h s o m t v s j z p E l l h a y o n f x h a m u m i h t v s r j z p a p
 a l u m i f ? t v s j z p a l u m i f E s h t v s a y ; j i c i f t a l u m i f & i f w u l l a z n f y y g r n f /

t v s r j z p a p a l u m i f (4) y g ¹⁶

t v s a y ; y k k v o n f

- (1) a & s a & s b o w u t v s a y ; j i c i f t a v h t x r & j i c i f /
- (2) r r t a u l l y l l y p o n f O w k u e n f y g ; a e a o ; j i c i f /
- (3) u l l y l l y p o n f O w k u r v s & u E l l h a t m i f a u m i f r e h e j i c i f /
- (4) u l l y l l y p o n f O p i r s m ; u l e c r f o h r n f u l l p h & h e j i c i f [h o m t c s u (4) c s u f
& h e y g u t v s r j z p a j r m u E l l h a y /

t v s j z p a l u m i f t * f (3) y g ¹⁷

- (1) v s z G O w k & j i c i f /
- (2) t v s c y k k & j i c i f /
- (3) o ' g w & m ; & j i c i f [h o m t c s u (3) y g ; E s h j y n p l y g u t v s j z p a j r m u E l l b o n f
p t c s u (3) y g ; w l l v n f o ' g w & m ; o n f & t ? j z p t b o n f /

t v s a y ; j i c i f t a l u m i f & i f (8) r s ¹⁸

- (1) r r t k b l t v s c y k k h a m u f v m a o m a l u m i h a y ; v s j i c i f /
- (2) t u l l & r n h b ; ? t y g , h a b ; a l u m u f i a y ; v s j i c i f /
- (3) a & s u o l w p y g ; u a y ; c k t a o m a l u m i h , c k v p z e f r r d u j y e f i a y ; v s j i c i f /
- (4) a e m i f t c g r r d t m ; t u s h & v l r n f [l i a y ; v s j i c i f /

16/ p & d m ? | ? 318 /

17/ E w l | ? 296 /

18/ ' 0 3 ? 214 /

- (3) tvšcyk'wv u ovr& tvšay;yk'wvuvnf; ovr& Owkypinf;uvnf; rpiMu, ? uhuftustuh r, Nunbl apwemrxubeaomt vsonf v, f, majrnlu raumi faom ršaptsoubltusthr&ay/
- (4) tvšay;yk'wvES h tvšcyk'wv wv EšOĐvH ovr&šyĐ Owkypinf;uvnf; pilmu, f um uhuftustuh , NunjyĐ apwemxubešygu v, f, majraumi fū ršaplaumi fuplufyštoubltustšay;MubjrwN/

obawmāumi fwh'nbnf rñāaumi fust? olwyg;wñāaumi fust [bom twES h y&rŵatmif aqmi &GūMūonfrñ "rŵmyijzponf/ xñāMūmi h tvšjy&mwŵlvnf; obawmāumi fwbñf taMūmi f(5)yg;uññhŵvātmi fyk' ay;všMūonf/

obawmāumi fwh' tvš(5) rš²³

- (1) všzG DwkulpiMu, āumi frēātmi f jlyi fi všjci f/
- (2) všzG Dwr tvšcyk'wv ułpwłxłwŵ f tav; tjrwxm; i všjci f/
- (3) b0ršvŵvājrmuā&; uñ&n&G jyĐ rñāuñ wñ f v ušzi h všjci f/
- (4) tMūG f; t ušf [kwbl * &kwplufykt yāom ypñf wñ u všjci f/
- (5) ÓPūllā&šōñ; jyk' ay; všjci f; wñ jzponf/

avmuwŵf "r? t "r? &fwāeoubll obawmES h roawm wñbnf; tjrłwn&š aelūonf/ oñonf obawmāumi fwbñf 'gejy&mū aumi frēātmi f jlyi āqmi &Gūf aomlvnf; roawm wñbnf; vsonf [kqumrwjykw wñūayonf/ xñāMūmi h roawm wñ tvš, kw(5) rš t m; wi fyygrñf/

tvš, kw(5) rš²⁴

- (1) všzG DwkulpiMu, āumi frēātmi f pñr&š všjci f/
- (2) všzG Dwr tvšcyk'wv uł tav; tjrwxm; bl všjci f/
- (3) rñāušzi huñ wñ huñ i us ray; všjci f/
- (4) xri f ušf [i f ušf pēly pft yāom ypñf wñ u všjci f/
- (5) ÓP rqi jci bl vš' ge f jci f; wñ jzponf/

tvš' ge [bnf ypñf; Opñjynpñš jylēñ bnf [kw? olwpyg; tm; aumi fust cšfomjz pāponf q&žzi h 'geajrmuāyonf/ tvš' gejylenf; onf; vēpñta&MūĐ ayonf/ xñāMūmi h tvš' gejylenf; ulvnf; wi fyygrñf/

23/ r? 3? 74/
 t? 2? 152/
 24/ t? 2? 151/

tvšylenf(4)rš

- (1) tcaomoboni rrbomvftvšy/\ olwpyg;uñ ay;vš&ef rwlwšwef;ay/
xblonfjzpv&mb0wšf pñf;ptšpñmŁg Daomvñf; tjctt &ñjynpñ
- (2) tcaomoboni rñum;ray;vš/ olwpyg;uñ vš&efwšwef;\ xblonf
jzpv&mb0ü Opñrjynpñomvñf; tjctt &ñ&bwñsm;\
- (3) tcaomoboni uñ fwlšvñf;vš/\ olwpyg;uñvñf; vš&efwšwef;\/
xblonfjzpv&mb0wšf Opñrjynpñpñyñ tjctt &ñvñf; jynpñ/\
- (4) tcaomoboni uñ fwlšvñf;rvš? olwpyg;uñvñf; rwlwšwef? xblonf
jzpv&mb0wšf y pñf;Opñ rjynpñ tjctt &ñvñf;uñf;\

jrwpñb&m;&š fu y&Ńg&ygvšwñvšf rvštyšom tvšrsm; talumi f; uñ a [mlum;
xm; ygonf

rvštyšomt vš(5)rš²⁵

- (1) rñ, pšpwwšomtvš (rZšge)
- (2) Zmwš &yšo;? tñ rñtvš (orZšge)
- (3) umr *Pšpñm; ap&ef ršf;rtvš (Ewšge)
- (4) Eñ;rrsm;tv, ü Eñ;xšvñwšciftvš (Ńob'ge)
- (5) pšvñwšwšpwwšompmEš h''mvñyñum;csyftvš (pšvñur[®]ge)wñjzponf
tcašftcgulwšwšf tcašboñtcašboñf vš'gef;Eñ šom tvš'geršvñf; &šo;
onf ðif;uñumv'ge [šac: onf

umv'ge(5)rš²⁶

- (1) {ñbñf;sm;tñ; aušaršvš'gef;jcif; (tm*Eñu'ge)
- (2) cššoñ;rsñ;uñaušaršvš'gef;jcif; (*ñu'ge)
- (3) emruseš;í a&m*guyš&mušbñsm;uñvš'gef;jcif; (*ñme'ge)
- (4) qif;&bñsm;uñjrišjzišay;uršvš'gef;jcif; ('ñu[®]ge)
- (5) jrwsšomtvšcyš'švftm; oššpñm;Ńšvš'gef;jcif; (ošvšEššv'ge)wñjzponf

2;3/ apwem(3)wef

tvšay;yšñvñf

- (1) yššapwem - a&ššpñvšvñomubñwšpšvšay;jcif;/
- (2) rñšapwem - všcsišwšpšvšay;jcif; talumi hrysuf;uñvš'gef;jcif;/
- (3) tyšapwem - vš'gef;yššomuf Ńršajrmu&ñvšpñjziš h aemuxyñ vš'gef;jcif
[šom apwemxubššom tustay;ñubš; šayonf²⁷

25/ Ńš 3? 231/
26/ tñ 2? 35/

yAapwemESh ty&apwemrsm;u y#baEtusdu ay;Ehlygon/ yAapwem? ty&apwemxubeboni ublvjclif jrijrwaom txuweipm;ublvjzpon/ tcd rfn yAapwemjycluwof OrfajrmuOrfomr&Eajrmwclwjcif? wpplvpm&mtwuf raus reyjzpcif? rdtPbowiMdapvcif? xiay:ausnapmvcif tp&homtublv pdvrs; a&baqmihaeon/ ty&apwemrsvnf jylrdvmrfr;avjcif [kESvhoof romr, m jzpon/ xlbom ublvboni tublvjclhaejzih , kvfnhom atmufveipm; ublvjzpon/ yAapwem cshwlygu yxrt&g li ypinfOpincshwjcif? &lyqift*lj cshwjcif [hom tushw&m;rs;uH &&llwayon/ om'utm;jzihylygyD r&om;oni yapuAKgt&Sjrwftm; rvsrd raueyaoma'goplvjzih Muntrjcif [hom yAapwem cshwlvhalmumih t&lyqitustnfwebool a&mu&clbnf²⁸ rlapwemcshwlygu wrvef b0wof t*ljajcvutshwjcif? , kwfnhomtrshwlyzpcif? webtmPm ao;ofjcif; tushw&clayon/ b'umydvmed tavmitvsm obX;orboni twlvb0wpcckvof yapuAKgtm; &hlylyrsm; avmifvscjcif [hom rlapwemcshwlvclif wpcclom obX; ordb0wof cEmuH rs tvclqH0g;aom raumifaom&ellsm; xclay:clbn/ ty&apwemcshwlygu cshomluG Daom trshwlyzpc&aomvnt; pntprOpimvluH clbm; ohaqmi vlvf&clif? pntprOpimqkvf, kvysupb&jcif [hom qHustul clbm;&ayon/ b&m;&Svuxuuf tykvaobX;Muboni twlvb0wpcckvof w*oocD yapuAKgt&Sjrwftm; rcljrwaomqclfuH vs'getjybaemuf & [efawmtoni tpm;aumifpm;jyD tybaerbyl [krfr; , Gfaom tluhjpum ty&apwem ysuluclbn/ 'ge\ tushalmumih obX;jzpcclomvnt; ty&apwem cshwlvhomalmumih pntprfrsm;uH ohaqmi vlvf&clol aoomtcg a&m&Di&bl usa&mutclbnf²⁹ xhalmumih vszG typinfrsm;uH yAapwem xubepfn aocsnjyiqijyD vsoihayon/ vbaeqtPuvnt; tvcllyk&vftay: Munfnb'gyfr;jcif? vszG Dwkay: o'gMunvif OrfajrmuH jzpcifoni rlapwemuH xubepaygon/ tvsa&putscclli uG Mclblaqclfrsm;uH ow&Orfenf; aejcif? auRargrhvmufi snuH alumi Muaejcifoni rlapwemuH tmenfapygon/ rlapwemtmenfygu tushay;rluH Ehlawmay/ vsjybaemuufvnt; rdtvsub ow&wllf Orfajrmu&ayrn/ xhalmumih apwemokyg; jynpfroni ta&Mubyon/ apwemokwef xubeplygrS' ge\ tushuH tjynht0 clbm;Ehfrnfjzpon/

2;4/ tEhfrhge

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- ÉwðkvÿygVðwñf (1961)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/
- Oy&ðPðot ygVðwñf (1995)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/
- "rÿ' ygVðwñf (yXar mbma*g)/ (1959)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/
- aywOwkt ygVðwñf (1995)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/

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- OðmOwkt | ux m/ (1995)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/
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- Éwðkvát | ux m/ (1958)/ &efule! omoema&;OðpðXme/
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- jre! rmpmtzð jre! mt bð' meft uðf, ckyf (1979)/ &efule! pmay Æ r me f y ð; w; l; u; f
- vð ð n? ar m i f (OZ ð? oð ð? eðvd ðu; r ðes havmueðvd (1992)/ &efule! cð v i f j y a t m z f q u f y ð; w; l; u; f
- [kvðe! Oð? y' wfr f ðom [hom ygVjre! mt bð' me/ (1959)/ &efule! y ð; w; l; u; f; a; e; s; ð; m a; u; d; d; m X me/